

Experimental and numerical analysis of wet channels for evaporative cooling systems manufactured with polymeric film materials

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ABSTRACT

Evaporative cooling systems have emerged as a sustainable alternative to conventional air-cooling methods, offering reduced energy consumption and environmental impact. This study evaluated the performance of four evaporative cooling channels manufactured using innovative polymeric films with varying porosities and compositions. Material characterization, including microstructure, surface roughness, and water absorption capacities, was systematically performed to identify critical properties affecting evaporative efficiency. Experimental analyses under controlled inlet air conditions identified the channel made of non-woven polypropylene produced by the spunlace technique as exhibiting the highest wet bulb effectiveness (80.6 %). Subsequently, a numerical model based on the effectiveness–number of transfer units (ϵ -NTU) method was developed, validated against experimental results, and utilized to optimize channel geometry and operational conditions. The numerical model indicated that increasing channel length significantly enhances cooling performance up to a saturation point at a channel length-to-free passage area of 1229 m⁻¹, beyond which further improvements are marginal. These findings provide valuable guidelines for the design and optimization of polymer-based evaporative cooling systems, aiming to balance material properties, geometric factors, and operating conditions for maximum cooling efficiency and sustainability.

Nomenclature

a	slope of the temperature-enthalpy saturation line [kJ/kg·K]
A_p	free passage area [m ²]
\dot{C}	heat capacity rate [kg/s]
cp	specific heat capacity [kJ/kg·K]
D	diameter [m]
f	friction factor
h	specific enthalpy [kJ/kg]
k	thermal conductivity [W/m·K]
L	length [m]
\dot{m}	mass flow [kg/s]
m	mass [kg]
N	number of computational elements
Nu	Nusselt's number
P	total pressure drop [Pa]
\dot{q}	heat obtained with the numerical model [W]

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\dot{Q}	heat obtained with the performance analysis [W]
Q	energy [kJ/m ²]
R	roughness [μ m]
Ra	arithmetic mean deviation of a profile within the reference length [μ m]
Rc	mean height of a profile within the reference length [μ m]
Re	Reynolds number
Rz	maximum height of a profile within the reference length [μ m]
S	primary surface [μ m]
Sa	arithmetic mean deviation of the entire surface [μ m]
SA	surface area [m ² /g]
Sq	root mean square height of the entire surface [μ m]
Sz	maximum height of the entire surface [μ m]
t	time [min]
T	temperature [°C]
U	overall heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² ·K]
u	air velocity of the numerical model [m/s]

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V	air velocity during the performance analysis [m/s]
<i>Greek letters</i>	
Δ	differential
α_c	convective heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² ·K]
α_c	mass transfer coefficient between working air and water film [kg/m ² ·s]
β	mass transfer coefficient for water vapor [kg/m ² ·s]
δ	thickness [m]
ε	effectiveness [–]
μ	dynamic viscosity [kg/m·s]
ρ	density [kg/m ³]
τ	minor loss coefficient
σ	surface wetting factor [–]
ω	humidity ratio [kg/kg]
<i>Subscripts</i>	
amb	ambient
aux	auxiliary
d	dew point
f	friction loss
h	hydraulic
i	number of computational elements
in	inlet
int	interior of the channel
l	latent
m	minor loss
max	maximum
min	minimum
o	outlet
s	sensible
sat	saturated
t	total
water	water
wall	wall of the channel
wb	wet bulb
<i>Acronyms</i>	
AC	air channel
AHU	air handling unit
AM	additive manufacturing
CBA	chemical blowing agent
DEC	direct evaporative cooling
EC	evaporative cooling
EES	engineering equation solver
FC	flow conditioner
IEC	indirect evaporative cooling
NZEBs	net-zero energy buildings
NTU	number of transfer units
PE	polyethylene
PP	polypropylene
PT	pitot tube
PVA	polyvinyl alcohol
SEM	scanning electron spectroscopy
TC	thermal camera
WoC	wood chips

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, global energy demand has risen by 15 %, signalling significant growth across various sectors, notably within the building sector [1]. This sector, in particular, has seen a substantial increase in energy consumption to meet the escalating requirements for heating and cooling spaces. This rise can be attributed to several key factors, including the increase in global temperatures, the intensification of extreme weather events, and improving living standards in emerging markets [2]. Climate change has exacerbated the frequency and severity of extreme heat and cold waves, further driving the demand for climate control systems across broader regions. For instance, in 2023, approximately 800 TWh of electricity was consumed solely for cooling during periods of extreme heat, compared to less than 300 TWh needed for this purpose in the 1990s [1]. This growing burden highlights the urgent need for alternative cooling strategies capable of reducing electricity consumption while maintaining thermal comfort. Among the most promising approaches are energy-efficient and sustainable solutions that can be readily integrated into buildings, particularly in the context of Net Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs) [3].

NZEBs incorporate renewable energy sources and advanced energy-saving technologies to minimize overall consumption. Within this framework, evaporative cooling (EC) systems are attracting growing interest as a low-energy alternative to traditional vapor compression systems [4]. Unlike conventional air-conditioning, EC reduces air temperature through water evaporation [5], lowering energy consumption by up to a 66 % [6]. Direct evaporative cooling (DEC), in particular, is considered one of the most efficient and sustainable cooling methods available for buildings. In this process, warm air passes through water-saturated porous panels (wet channels), the water absorbs the sensible heat from the air and evaporates, thus reducing its temperature, so the sensible heat is converted into latent heat. A key advantage of DEC systems is their ability to cool air temperature down to its wet bulb temperature, maximizing cooling efficiency, particularly in dry climates [7].

The most commonly used DEC systems are typically constructed from metallic materials. A comparative review by various authors analysed the cooling performance of metallic, organic (cellulose), and inorganic (kraft paper) pads under identical inlet air conditions. The results demonstrated that inorganic pads achieved the lowest outlet temperature, recording 29.58 °C compared to 37.10 °C for metallic pads [8]. Key parameters affecting the cooling capacity of evaporative systems include wetting conditions, water evaporation rate, and geometry, all of which can be optimized through appropriate material selection [9]. Some researchers evaluated the performance of EC systems using two types of cellulose pads with different geometries, under varying air velocities and water flow rates. The results showed that pads with larger geometries provided higher cooling efficiency [10]. Other authors employed corrugated cellulose pads due to their good wetting and mass-transfer properties. However, their efficiency typically ranges between 0.64 and 0.70 under representative air velocities (1–1.5 m/s) [11]. Khosravi et al. conducted an experimental investigation on different natural EC pad materials used in a DEC system. Among the tested materials, wood chips (WoC) demonstrated the best performance in terms of cooling efficiency [12].

Furthermore, wet channels of regenerative Indirect Evaporative Cooling (IEC) systems, were manufactured using polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) combined with felt exhibited rapid and high water absorption rates due to their elevated surface roughness [13]. Comparative studies on porous materials for EC pads revealed that palash and coconut filaments achieved up to 26.3 % higher cooling effectiveness compared to conventional aspen and khus filaments [14]. Other authors carried out capillarity tests on three water-absorbing porous materials: nonwoven fabric, polyester filament, and cotton fibre, showing that polyester fibre achieved a significantly higher absorption height, resulting in greater temperature reduction [15]. Castillo-González et al. also investigated foam polymer materials fabricated through Additive Manufacturing (AM) as wetting materials in EC systems, concluding that higher porosity directly enhanced water absorption capacity and capillarity [16]. In addition, Tripathi et al. (2025) evaluated the dynamic thermal performance of a novel wet channel for evaporative cooling systems, demonstrating its critical role in improving heat and mass transfer under varying operating conditions [17].

Recent investigations have examined various parameters of EC systems to enhance their thermal behaviour. Previous studies explored the energy performance of air passage wet channel structures made from foam materials was investigated [18]. It was concluded that the channel with higher porosity achieved greater evaporative cooling capacity and the highest wet-bulb effectiveness of 0.86. Xu et al. analysed the influence of air velocity variation on IEC system performance, demonstrating that lower air velocities resulted in reduced outlet air temperatures [19]. A novel hybrid air-cooling system combining a desiccant wheel with a dew-point indirect evaporative cooler was experimentally investigated. The system achieved a sensible cooling capacity of 21.49 kW with an inlet air temperature of 45.9 °C and a humidity ratio of 7.91 g kg⁻¹, demonstrating its potential for high-performance cooling in hot and dry

climates [20]. Other study experimentally evaluated a novel solar-assisted indirect evaporative cooling system with a wet channel, achieving wet-bulb effectiveness values up to 90 % under high inlet temperature and low air flow rate conditions [21]. Furthermore, numerous works have carried out numerical modelling of heat and mass transfer processes in EC systems, often validating their results against experimental data [22]. Nemati et al. presented an effectiveness (ϵ) and Number of Transfer Units (NTU) model to an IEC, which was validated against available experimental and numerical data, showing that increasing the system length reduced outlet air temperature and water consumption [23]. A validated experimental model was used to assess how changes in operating conditions and exchanger geometry affect the thermal performance of different heat exchanger types [24]. Another study identified an optimal air channel length that minimized the outlet air temperature, contributing to the geometric optimization of the cooler [25].

Wet channel is the core component of any EC system, as it governs the heat and mass transfer processes that determine cooling effectiveness. The selection of channel materials is therefore critical, since their properties, such as water retention capacity, surface roughness, and porosity, directly influence evaporative cooling performance. Despite the growing interest in energy-efficient cooling, there remains a significant lack of studies focused on the fabrication and energy characterization of polymeric wet channels. This work addresses that gap through the development of innovative polymeric films bonded by lamination to achieve minimal wall thickness, enhancing the evaporative exchange process. The main objective of this study is to fabricate and experimentally evaluate four polymeric film channels with different porosities under controlled inlet air conditions. In parallel, a numerical model based on the ϵ -NTU method was developed. First, the model was calibrated and validated against experimental results to ensure its predictive reliability. Subsequently, the model was employed to optimize key geometric parameters, aiming to maximize evaporative cooling efficiency.

2. Methodology

The methodology followed in this work is summarized in Fig. 1. First, the polymer films were characterized to evaluate their microstructure, surface roughness, and water absorption properties. Second, an experimental evaluation of the fabricated wet channels was performed under controlled inlet air conditions, determining the outlet air temperatures, cooling capacity, and wet bulb effectiveness. Third, the model based on the ϵ -NTU method was calibrated and validated against experimental data, and finally the channel design optimization under different operating conditions (velocity, length and outlet temperature).

2.1. Manufacturing of film materials

Four air passage channels were manufactured using polymeric film materials. Each channel was composed of a hydrophobic outer layer, made in all cases from pure polyethylene (PE), and an inner hydrophilic layer, whose composition varied as follows: (a) C1: The interior layer

was composed of additive-enhanced PE with a chemical blowing agent (CBA) at a concentration of 2 %, creating a porous structure due to gas release during the melting process; (b) C2: This channel was composed of non-woven polypropylene (PP) manufactured using the spunlace technique, which involves entangling filaments through high-pressure water jets to produce a strong, durable, and porous material; (c) C3: The channel interior was made from cellulose (absorbent paper); (d) C4: The inner layer of this channel was a bilayer material composed of an intermediate cellulose layer bonded to a layer of non-woven PP. The inner and outer layers were bonded together with a laminator (7000 PLUS 7000 L, GBC, EU) operating at low temperature (75 °C). Each channel had dimensions of 310 mm length, 136 mm width and 4.5 mm thickness, it features external partition walls, resulting in a free passage area (A_p) of 487.9 mm² through which the air can circulate. The characteristics of each channel are shown in Table 1 and an image of each channel can be observed in Fig. 2.

2.2. Characterization of film materials

Several characterization tests were carried out for each hydrophilic material from the inner layers of each channel to evaluate their surface structure and water retention capacity, as these parameters strongly influence the evaporative cooling performance. The microstructure and morphology of the samples were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-7800 F model, Jeol, Japan) with square samples of 10 mm per side. Roughness and primary surface of the materials were analysed using a confocal and interferometric microscope (DCM8, Leica, Spain). The following parameters were measured: (a) Maximum height, Rz: represents the sum of the maximum peak height and the maximum valley depth of a profile within the reference length; (b) Mean height, Rc: represents the mean for the height of a profile within the reference length; (c) Arithmetic mean deviation, Ra: represents the arithmetic mean of the absolute ordinate within the reference length (d) Maximum height, Sz: is equivalent to the sum of the maximum peak height and maximum valley depth (e) Arithmetical mean height, Sa: represents the arithmetical mean of the entire surface; (f) Root mean square height, Sq: represents the root mean square of the entire surface. Additionally, water absorption tests were conducted to characterize the ability of the porous polymeric material to absorb and distribute water. Two methods

Table 1
Technical characteristics of the channels C1, C2, C3 and C4.

	C1	C2	C3	C4
External material	PE	PE	PE	PE
Intermediate material	-	-	-	Cellulose
Internal material	Additive-enhanced PE	Non-woven PP	Cellulose	Non-woven PP
Superficial density [g/m ²]	5.7	100	70	150
Total wall thickness [mm]	0.12	0.4	0.25	0.6

Fig. 1. Flowchart representation of the research methodology.

Fig. 2. Manufactured air channels: (from left to right) C1, C2, C3, and C4.

were employed: capillarity and immersion. The capillarity test evaluates the water absorption rate driven by capillary forces. Specimens measuring $80 \times 15 \times 0.8$ mm were placed vertically into a dyed water bath, and the test was performed until the capillary rise ceased, approximately 1 h after the start of the experiment. In the immersion test, the specimens were fully submerged in water for 30 min. To determine the total water absorption, each sample was weighed before and immediately after immersion.

2.3. Experimental setup

The energy performance of the channels was evaluated through experimental tests conducted in the air conditioning laboratory at the University of Córdoba. The experimental setup included an Air Handling Unit (AHU), a network of ducts, and a data acquisition system. The AHU

enabled precise control of the inlet air conditions, including air temperature, relative humidity, and air flow rate. The setup featured various sensors to assess the energy performance of each channel, such as dry bulb temperature sensors (T), dew point temperature sensors (T_d), and differential pressure sensors (ΔP). Additionally, a thermal camera (TC) was employed to visualize the thermal behaviour of each channel, see Fig. 3. The technical specifications of the sensors used are shown in Table 2.

Each test began by adjusting the air inlet conditions and allowing stabilization at an inlet temperature (T_{in}) of 40°C , a dew point temperature ($T_{d,in}$) of 10°C , an air velocity (V_{in}) of 9.4 m/s , maintaining the ambient temperature constant at 24°C . The air inlet conditions were selected to represent a realistic hot-dry climatic scenario, typical of arid and semi-arid regions across southern Europe, North Africa, and southwest Asia [26]. Prior to the test, each channel was submerged in

Fig. 3. Experimental setup.

Table 2
Technical specifications of the sensors.

Variable	Type of sensor	Manufacturer	Accuracy
T	RTD 4-wire temperature sensor model T-100	GE Measurement & Control Solutions	± 0.5 °C (-40 °C–125 °C)
T_d	Chilled mirror hygrometer model 1111H	GE Measurement & Control Solutions	± 0.2 °C (-25 °C–65 °C)
ΔP	Differential pressure transmitter	Siemens	± 5 % (at range <500 Pa)
TC	Thermal camera	Flir One Pro	± 3 °C (5 °C–120 °C)

water for 30 min, after which excess water was removed. Subsequently, the channel was connected to the ducts system linked to the AHU. The test lasted 30 min, during which inlet and outlet parameters were recorded every 3 s using a datalogger.

The experimental thermal behaviour of the channels was evaluated using the following parameters.

- Sensible heat (\dot{Q}_s) delivered by the channel structure was calculated according to Eq. (1). It was determined as the mass air flow rate (\dot{m}) multiplied by the difference between specific enthalpies of auxiliary and inlet air ($h_{aux} - h_{in}$). The auxiliary state was defined as having the same dry bulb temperature as the outlet air and the same humidity ratio as the inlet air.

$$\dot{Q}_s = \dot{m} \cdot (h_{aux} - h_{in}) \quad (1)$$

- Latent heat (\dot{Q}_l) delivered by the channel structure was obtained using Eq. (2). It was calculated as mass air flow rate (\dot{m}) multiplied by the difference between specific enthalpies of the auxiliary state and the outlet air ($h_o - h_{aux}$).

$$\dot{Q}_l = \dot{m} \cdot (h_o - h_{aux}) \quad (2)$$

- Wet bulb effectiveness (ϵ_{wb}) was calculated as the ratio between the difference of inlet (T_{in}) and outlet (T_o) dry bulb temperatures to the difference between T_{in} and inlet wet bulb temperature ($T_{wb,in}$), obtained with Eq. (3)

$$\epsilon_{wb} = \frac{T_{in} - T_o}{T_{in} - T_{wb,in}} \quad (3)$$

After analysing the four channels, the best performance channel was selected based on the lowest outlet temperature and highest wet bulb effectiveness. Subsequently, twelve experimental tests were conducted exclusively for the selected channel and were used to validate a detailed numerical model for an air channel, see in Table 3.

Table 3
Experimental test to validate the numerical model.

Test	T_{in} [°C]	$T_{d,in}$ [°C]	V_{in} [m/s]
1	30	13	9.4
2	30	10	13.5
3	33	10	17.6
4	33	10	9.4
5	35	13	13.5
6	35	13	17.6
7	37	10	9.4
8	37	13	17.6
9	39	13	13.5
10	39	10	17.6
11	40	13	17.6
12	40	10	9.4

2.4. Detailed channel model

A detailed numerical model of the air channel has been developed based on the ϵ -NTU method. Previous studies have generally focused solely on DEC or IEC models [27,28], while this work presents a detailed model specifically adapted to the characteristics of the studied air wet channel. The following assumptions were adopted to simplify the heat exchanger analysis: (i) Heat losses to the surroundings were neglected; (ii) Heat and mass transfer coefficients, were considered uniform within each sub-channel; (iii) The Reynolds analogy was assumed valid, and the Lewis number (Le) was assumed to be unity; (iv) The thermal resistance at the air-water interface was considered negligible, implying that the interface temperature was equal to the saturation temperature of the water film; (v) Ambient temperature was assumed constant throughout the analysis; (vi) Given the assumption of constant ambient temperature, the thermal capacitance rate of ambient air was set significantly higher than that inside the channel, thus ensuring negligible ambient temperature variation; (vii) Ambient air velocity was considered constant and negligible relative to the substantially higher air velocity inside the channel; hence, free convection was assumed only at the top surface, while all other faces were considered adiabatic.

The method solution method consisted of dividing the channel into N numbers of computational elements, as shown in Fig. 4. The numerical problem was implemented in Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software (v.11.982) [29]. This model allowed to predict the outlet air conditions or determine the required channel length based on pre-defined inlet air parameters.

The following equations represented the fundamental mass and energy balance relations used in classical heat-exchanger theory [30]:

Sensible heat (\dot{q}_s) and latent heat (\dot{q}_l) were calculated based on the energy balance of the air within the channel as shown in Eq. (4) and Eq. (5). Where h_1 and h_{N+1} represented the enthalpies of the air at the inlet and outlet states of each element respectively. $h_{aux,N+1}$ was the auxiliary state with the same dry bulb temperature as the inlet air and the same humidity ratio as the outlet air. Total heat (\dot{q}_t) was calculated as the sum of both, sensible heat and latent heat (Eq. (6)).

$$\dot{q}_s = \dot{m} \cdot (h_1 - h_{aux,N+1}) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{q}_l = \dot{m} \cdot (h_{N+1} - h_{aux,N+1}) \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{q}_t = \dot{q}_s + \dot{q}_l \quad (6)$$

The mass transfer coefficient for water vapor from the water film to the air stream of each computational element (β_i) was calculated by multiplying the surface wetting factor (σ), was estimated as 0.88, based on thermographic image analysis, reflecting the fraction of the surface that remained wetted at the time of maximum cooling performance, with the mass transfer coefficient between working air and water film of each computational element ($\alpha_{m,i}$), as seen in Eq. (7).

$$\beta_i = \alpha_{m,i} \cdot \sigma \quad (7)$$

The local convective heat transfer coefficient inside the channel of each computational element ($\alpha_{c,i}$) was the multiplication of the Nusselt's number of each computational element (Nu_i) and the specific heat capacity of each computational element (k_i), divided by the hydraulic diameter of the channel (D_h), obtained with Eq. (8). Nu_i was calculated through an EES function *Ductflow_n_local* [29] which depends on Reynolds number, Prandtl number, x_i/D_h , aspect ratio and relative roughness. The local convective heat transfer coefficient in the ambient ($\alpha_{c,amb}$) was the multiplication of the Nusselt's number in the ambient (Nu_{amb}) and the specific heat capacity in the ambient (k_{amb}), divided by D_h , as shown in Eq. (9). Nu_{amb} was calculated through an EES function *FCPlateHorizontal1* [29] for a horizontal flat plate that is downward cooled.

$$\alpha_{c,i} = \frac{Nu_i \cdot k_i}{D_h} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram presenting the computational elements for numerical modelling.

$$\alpha_{c,amb} = \frac{Nu_{amb} \cdot k_{amb}}{D_h} \quad (9)$$

The mass transfer coefficient between working air and water film of each computational element ($\alpha_{m,i}$) was calculated as the ratio between $\alpha_{c,i}$ and the mean specific heat capacity of each computational element $\bar{C}_{p,i}$ (Eq. (10)), as seen in Eq. (11).

$$\bar{C}_{p,i} = \frac{c_{p,i} + c_{p,i+1}}{2} \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_{m,i} = \frac{\alpha_{c,i}}{\bar{C}_{p,i}} \quad (11)$$

The Reynold's number of each computational element (Re_i) was obtained as the multiplication between air velocity in the interior of the channel (u), D_h and the mean density of each computational element $\bar{\rho}_i$ (Eq. (12)), divided by the mean dynamic viscosity of each computational element $\bar{\mu}_i$ (Eq. (13)), with Eq. (14).

$$\bar{\rho}_i = \frac{\rho_i + \rho_{i+1}}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\mu}_i = \frac{\mu_i + \mu_{i+1}}{2} \quad (13)$$

$$Re_i = \frac{u \cdot D_h \cdot \bar{\rho}_i}{\bar{\mu}_i} \quad (14)$$

The heat capacity rate for the interior of the channel (\dot{C}_{int}) was mass air flow rate (\dot{m}), and the heat capacity rate for the ambient (\dot{C}_{amb}) was much larger than \dot{C}_{int} because the ambient was a constant temperature, were defined by Eq. (15) and Eq. (16).

$$\dot{C}_{int} = \dot{m} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{C}_{amb} = 1000 \cdot \dot{C}_{int} \quad (16)$$

The slope of the temperature-enthalpy saturation line of each computational element (a_i) was the ratio between the difference of the saturation enthalpies of each computational element ($h_{s,i} - h_{s,i+1}$), and the difference of temperatures of each computational element ($T_i - T_{i+1}$), see Eq. (17).

$$a_i = \frac{h_{sat,i} - h_{sat,i+1}}{T_i - T_{i+1}} \quad (17)$$

The effectiveness of each computational element (ε_i) was calculated using Eq. (18) as the ratio between \dot{q}_T/N and the product of $Min(\dot{C}_{int}, \dot{C}_{amb})$ and the difference of the saturation enthalpy of each computational element and the specific ambient enthalpy ($h_{sat,i} - h_{amb}$).

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{\dot{q}_T/N}{Min(\dot{C}_{int}, \dot{C}_{amb}) \cdot (h_{sat,i} - h_{amb})} \quad (18)$$

The Number of Transfer Units of each computational element (NTU_i) was calculated using *Parallelflow* function [29], as the system involved two fluids flowing in the same direction, which depended on ε_i , \dot{C}_{int} and \dot{C}_{amb} . The overall heat transfer coefficient of each computational element (U_i) was computed by Eq. (19). Where wall thickness (δ_{wall}) was measured (Table 1), thermal wall conductivity (k_{wall}) was 0.53

$Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$, thermal conductivity of water film (k_{water}) was $0.3 Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ and water film thickness (δ_{water}) was estimated at approximately 0.3 mm based on the experimentally measured water retention of the channel, corresponding to the equivalent layer formed over the wetted surface.

$$U_i = \frac{1}{a_i \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_{c,amb}} + \frac{\delta_{wall}}{k_{wall}} + \frac{\delta_{water}}{k_{water}} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta_i}} \quad (19)$$

The total pressure drop (ΔP) was the sum of friction loss (ΔP_f) and minor loss (ΔP_m), obtained by Eq. (20).

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_f + \Delta P_m = f \cdot \frac{\rho \cdot u^2 \cdot L}{2 \cdot D_h} + \sum \tau \cdot \frac{\rho \cdot u^2}{2} \quad (20)$$

The nonlinear system of equations was solved in EES using its default implicit iterative Newton-based algorithm. Convergence was achieved when the residuals of all governing equations were below 10^{-6} , ensuring numerical stability and consistency of the solution.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material analysis

3.1.1. Microstructure characterization

The SEM images of the four hydrophilic material samples captured at a magnification corresponding to a scale bar of 500 μm are shown in Fig. 5. It was observed significant differences in the microstructures of the analysed materials, which directly influenced their water absorption and retention capacities, key characteristics for evaporative cooling systems.

Sample C1 (see Fig. 5a) exhibited a relatively smooth and homogeneous surface with minimal porosity and an absence of visible filaments or irregularities. This morphology restricted both water absorption and retention due to the lack of surface roughness and interconnected porous networks that would facilitate water adhesion and transport. In contrast, sample C2 (see Fig. 5b) showed an open and highly porous structure characterized by interconnected voids, enabling efficient water transport. This microstructure provided a large specific surface area, thereby enhancing both water distribution and evaporation. The greater availability of open spaces supported the capillary movement of water, making this material especially suitable for evaporative cooling applications. Sample C3 (see Fig. 5c) featured a fibrous structure composed of interwoven filaments, however, this arrangement appeared denser and more compact compared to the open structure observed in C2. While this structure still facilitated water absorption and retention, the denser arrangement may slightly reduce its overall efficiency in water distribution and evaporation compared to C2. Lastly, sample C4 (see Fig. 5d) a heterogeneous porous structure with considerable gaps between the filaments, interspersed with solid areas where filaments appeared fused together. This morphology provided intermediate characteristics, potentially influencing water absorption and evaporation rates differently compared to the other samples.

3.1.2. Analysis of roughness and primary surface

The roughness and primary surface measurements for each material are shown in Table 4. Based on the evaluated parameters, two distinct groups were identified: samples C2 and C4 exhibited the highest values

Fig. 5. Images obtained by SEM.

Table 4
Results of roughness and primary surface of the materials.

Materials	C1	C2	C3	C4
Rz [μm]	34.56	101.02	21.53	68.72
Rc [μm]	18.76	51.57	13.80	33.64
Ra [μm]	5.38	13.95	3.35	9.64
Sz [μm]	144.92	448.79	67.70	366.45
Sa [μm]	11.65	24.01	7.96	18.49
Sq [μm]	16.79	36.00	10.16	26.76

across all roughness (Rz, Rc, Ra) and surface (Sz, Sa, Sq) parameters, indicating significantly greater surface and roughness. In contrast, samples C1 and C3 displayed consistently lower values, suggesting smoother and more uniform surfaces.

Fig. 6 presents the 3D topography of Sz for each sample, illustrating the distribution of peaks and valleys. Among the samples, C2 exhibited the highest Sz values, followed by C4, C1, and C3, reinforcing the distinction between rougher and smoother surfaces.

The greater surface roughness observed in samples C2 and C4 suggests their suitability for evaporative cooling applications. The increased surface irregularities contribute to a larger surface area and enhanced water retention due to microcavities, facilitating more effective evaporation. This characteristic is critical for optimizing heat dissipation and improving the cooling capacity.

3.1.3. Capillary and immersion water absorption analysis

The results of the capillarity test and the measured capillary rise height for each sample are presented in Fig. 7. It can be observed that sample C1, composed of additive-enhanced polyethylene (PE), demonstrated very limited capillarity, with the lowest capillary rise height of only 5 mm. This is consistent with the non-polar nature of PE, which inherently repels water molecules and limits hydrogen bonding. As a result, its hydrophobic character led to poor water absorption and limited retention capacity.

Regarding sample C2, made of non-woven polypropylene (PP), also a non-polar polymer, exhibited a considerably higher capillary rise height than C1, reaching 51 mm. This improved performance was primarily due to its highly porous structure and fibrous arrangement, as evidenced by SEM images in Fig. 5b, facilitating enhanced physical water entrapment despite its non-polar nature.

Samples C3 and C4 both achieved the maximum capillary rise height of 100 mm, indicating excellent capillary performance. Sample C3, composed entirely of cellulose, benefited significantly from its porous structure and the intrinsic polar nature of cellulose, enabling extensive hydrogen bonding and efficient water absorption. Sample C4, consisting of a bilayer structure combining cellulose and non-woven PP, demonstrated superior capillary action due to the synergistic interaction between layers. In this configuration, the non-woven PP provided structural stability and promoted physical water retention through its porous framework, while the cellulose layer contributed primarily to chemical water absorption through hydrogen bonding.

The results of the immersion test are presented in Table 5, showing

Fig. 6. Primary surface profiles (Sz) of the samples.

Fig. 7. Capillarity test and the capillary rise height for each sample.

the percentages of weight gain due to water absorption for each sample.

Sample C1 exhibited the lowest water absorption (42.3 %), consistent with the non-polar character of PE. Its limited porosity (Fig. 5a) and minimal surface density (5.7 g/m²) further reduced its overall water retention capability.

Sample C2, although is non-polar composition, displayed high water

(b) C2

(d) C4

Table 5
Summary of sample characteristics.

Samples	C1	C2	C3	C4
Capillary rise height	5 mm	51 mm	100 mm	100 mm
Material	Additive enhanced PE	Non-woven PP	Cellulose	Cellulose and non-woven PP
Polarity	Non-polar	Non-polar	Polar	Polar
Weight gain	42.3 %	145.4 %	77.4 %	233.6 %
Superficial density	5.7 g/m ²	100 g/m ²	70 g/m ²	150 g/m ²

absorption (145.4 %), primarily attributed to its larger and highly interconnected porous structure (Fig. 5b). This high porosity, combined with a relatively high surface density (100 g/m²), further enhanced its capacity to trap water, leading to substantial weight gain.

Sample C3 showed moderate water absorption (77.4 %), somewhat limited by smaller, more compact pores compared to samples C2 and C4, as well as a lower surface density (70 g/m²). Nevertheless, the polar nature of cellulose still supported substantial water absorption.

Sample C4 demonstrated the highest water absorption (233.6 %), driven by the combination of cellulose’s chemical affinity for water and the extreme porosity of the non-woven PP layer. Its high polarity makes cellulose strongly hydrophilic, binding water molecules tightly within its structure. Combined with its high surface density (150 g/m²), this led to the greatest weight gain among all tested samples.

3.2. Energy analysis

Fig. 8 illustrates the temporal evolution of the dry bulb temperature (T, continuous line) and the dew point temperature (T_d, dashed line) of the inlet and outlet air across four different channels (C1, C2, C3, and C4). The inlet conditions remained constant throughout the test duration. Below the graph, thermal images are presented, captured every 5 min, showing temperature distributions for each channel during the test

Fig. 8. Evolution of air dry bulb temperature (T) and air dew point temperature (T_d). Below, thermographic images illustrating the thermal evolution of each channel surface during the test period.

period.

Initially, a rapid decrease in outlet T was observed in all channels, this decrease was primarily attributed to the presence of retained water within the channels. As the water evaporated, it absorbed heat from the surrounding air, leading to a reduction in temperature. This cooling effect persisted until a minimum temperature was reached. Channels C2 and C4 achieved the lowest temperatures during this process, 24.2 °C and 24.9 °C, respectively. Subsequently, as the retained water was progressively depleted, outlet temperatures began to increase, signalling a reduction in the evaporative cooling effect. The temperature achieved by the channel in this study is consistent with previous findings, where a similar evaporative cooling effect was observed [18]. However, the use of film materials resulted in a lower outlet temperature under same operational conditions.

At the beginning of the test, the outlet T_d initially rose compared to the inlet value, as the air stream became humidified during the first stage of evaporation. As the test progresses, the T_d lines tended to stabilize at a lower value, reflecting the diminishing water content available for evaporation in each channel. Notably, the dew-point temperatures for channels C1 and C3 continued decreasing significantly over time; specifically, channel C1 reached the inlet T_d value by the end of the test, indicating complete drying. In contrast, channels C2 and C4 continued to exhibit relatively stable T_d values at the conclusion of the test, indicating prolonged water retention and sustained evaporative cooling. The thermographic images presented beneath the graph illustrate the evolution of surface temperatures and water evaporation for each channel. The lower temperature regions (purple/blue) corresponded to areas with ongoing evaporation (wet areas), while the higher

temperature regions (yellow/red) represented areas where evaporation had ceased, leading to heat accumulation (dry areas). The images showed that channel C1 reached higher surface temperatures in a shorter period of time, suggesting a faster water evaporation and an accelerated drying process. In contrast, channels C2 and C4 maintained lower surface temperatures for a longer period of time, indicating a prolonged water retention, which increased the evaporative cooling effect. When evaporation occurs, the water absorbs latent heat from the surface, resulting in localized cooling. The thermal behaviour of channel C3 was similar to that of C2 and C4. However, starting from minute 25, significant drying became evident, with half of its surface showing higher-temperature regions, indicative of reduced water availability.

It should be emphasized that the results in outlet temperature profiles are strongly influenced by the availability of water at the channel surface, rather than by the total absorption capacity (Table 5). In channel C2, the non-polar character of the polymer promotes the presence of free water films at the surface, which are readily evaporated and contribute effectively to cooling. Conversely, channel C4, being more polar, binds water more tightly within its bulk structure, thereby reducing its immediate availability for evaporation. This interpretation is consistent with the thermographic images, where channel C4 is observed to remain fully wetted for longer periods than C2.

Fig. 9 shows the sensible and latent heat values for each channel, evaluated at the point where the outlet dry-bulb temperature reached its minimum. Sensible heat represents the system's ability to lower the air temperature, while latent heat is associated with moisture uptake through evaporation. At this stage, the highest sensible power values were observed, as further cooling of the air required significant energy

Fig. 9. Overlay latent heat, sensible heat and wet bulb effectiveness for each channel.

exchange. Channels C2 and C4 recorded the highest values of both sensible and latent heat, as well as wet-bulb effectiveness, though with slight differences between them. Channel C2 exhibited higher sensible heat (58.1 W) and latent heat (67.2 W) than C4, highlighting its superior capacity for cooling the air. This behaviour suggests that the properties of C2 favoured more effective heat and mass transfer, resulting in a stronger evaporative effect. In line with this, C2 also achieved a slightly higher wet-bulb effectiveness (80.6 %) compared to C4 (78.2 %), indicating a more efficient use of energy for evaporative cooling. In contrast, C1 showed the lowest performance, with sensible heat of 37.2 W, latent heat of 28.0 W, and wet-bulb effectiveness of 46.5 %, confirming its limited cooling capacity and reduced moisture absorption through evaporation.

A comparative summary of the key performance metrics obtained for the four tested channels (C1–C4) is presented in Table 6.

3.3. Validation of the detailed numerical model

Additional experimental tests (Table 3) were conducted using the best-performing channel from the experimental analysis (channel C2). The results were then compared to the numerical predictions obtained with the mathematical model described in section 2.4. The numerical model was validated by comparing the dry bulb air temperature reduction values, ΔT_{num} , with the experimental values, ΔT_{exp} , as shown in Fig. 10. A detailed table comparing experimental and numerical outlet temperatures is provided in the Supplementary Material (Table 7). The results showed a strong agreement, with a coefficient of determination of R^2 equal to 0.9824, and most data points were within a $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ deviation. This confirms the high accuracy of the numerical model in replicating experimental data and validates its suitability for accurately predicting the thermal behaviour of the evaporative cooling channel.

Table 6

Key performance metrics.

Channels	C1	C2	C3	C4
T_{out}	29.9 °C	24.2 °C	26.9 °C	24.9 °C
\dot{Q}_s	37.2 W	58.1 W	48.3 W	55.6 W
\dot{Q}_l	28.0 W	67.2 W	48.8 W	61.4 W
ϵ_{wb}	46.5 %	80.6 %	63.4 %	78.2 %

Fig. 10. Comparison between experimental and numerical temperature differences ΔT .

3.4. Numerical optimization of wet channel design

A numerical model was developed to optimize the design of wet channels to enhance cooling performance. A computational analysis was performed to evaluate the influence of the number of computational elements on the numerical results. Fig. 11 shows the outlet dry bulb temperature (T_{out}) and sensible heat (\dot{Q}_s) of the channel predicted by the numerical model as a function of the number of computational elements (N). The inlet temperature was set at 40°C , the air velocity at 9.4 m/s , and the channel length at 0.31 m . The results indicated significant variations for lower N values. However, as N increased, both parameters tended to stabilize, suggesting numerical convergence, which was achieved for N greater than 30, with T_{out} and \dot{Q}_s stabilizing at 23.07°C and 58.3 W , respectively.

Fig. 12 illustrates the air dry bulb temperature (T) and the humidity ratio (ω) along the channel length (x/L) for $N = 30$. The results showed that the air temperature decreases progressively along the channel, starting at 40°C at the inlet and reaching 23.07°C at the outlet. Conversely, humidity ratio exhibited an increasing trend due to

Fig. 11. Outlet air dry bulb temperature and sensible heat as a function of the number of computational elements.

Fig. 12. Air dry bulb temperature and humidity ratio along the channel length.

evaporative cooling, as water vapor was added to the air.

In order to analyse the optimal channel design in terms of achieving the minimum outlet temperature (T_{out}), a 3D graph is shown in Fig. 13, T_{out} is represented as a function of channel length (L) and air velocity (V_{in}). The input variables were fixed at constant values: $T_{in} = 40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $N = 30$. The surface of the graph was represented with a colour gradient from red (higher temperatures) to dark blue (lower temperatures), to observe the thermal distribution under different operating conditions.

The results showed that as V_{in} increased, T_{out} tended to rise. This effect was attributed to the reduced contact time between the air and the wet surface, which limited the cooling potential. Conversely, increasing the channel length led to a progressive decrease in T_{out} across all V_{in}

Fig. 13. Variation of outlet temperature (T_{out}) as a function of channel length (L) and air velocity (V_{in}).

cases, suggesting that a longer path enhanced heat and mass transfer, allowing the air to reach lower temperatures. However, beyond $L = 0.6\text{ m}$, the temperature stabilized around $20.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, regardless of the air velocity. This indicated a thermal saturation point, where further increasing the channel length had a negligible effect on cooling performance. This corresponds to a L/A_p ratio, defined as the length divided by free passage area, equal to 1229 m^{-1} and ϵ_{wb} close to 97 %.

3.5. Limitations of this study

The results obtained in this work are valid for the specific polymeric channel configurations presented in Table 1 and for the inlet condition tested. The proposed model adequately predicts the behaviour of the wet channel within this range, although extrapolation to different boundary conditions requires further validation. However, it was formulated under the simplifying assumptions described in Section 2.4. Long-term effects such as material aging, biofouling, and scaling were not considered, despite their potential impact on evaporation and durability in practical applications. These aspects, together with extended operation ranges and multi-channel interactions, should be addressed in future work.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the evaporative cooling performance of four wet channels using different polymeric film materials of varying porosity and composition. Trough comprehensive material characterization, including SEM analysis, surface roughness, and water absorption capacity, the relationship between material properties and evaporative cooling efficiency was clearly established. Additionally, a numerical model based on the ϵ -NTU method was developed and successfully validated against the experimental data. Based on these results, the main conclusions of this work are.

- The material analysis showed that samples C2 (non-woven polypropylene) and C4 (cellulose combined with non-woven PP) exhibited interconnected pore structures characterized by considerable gaps between the filaments. These morphologies favoured water absorption and capillary transport, which was consistent with their behaviour in the absorption tests, where both samples achieved the highest weight gain. Roughness and primary surface measurements followed the same trend, indicating that C2 and C4, with greater surface irregularities, provided a larger effective surface area and improved water retention due to microcavities.
- The energy analysis revealed that channels C2 and C4 achieved the lowest outlet air temperatures ($24.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $24.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively) and exhibited the highest values of both sensible and latent heat transfer, confirming their superior evaporative cooling capacity. However, channel C2 achieved the highest wet bulb effectiveness (80.6 %), suggesting that C2 used the available energy more efficiently for evaporative cooling.
- The detailed model was developed to determine the optimal geometric design and operational parameters for channel C2. The results showed that reducing the air velocity led to lower outlet temperature. Additionally, extending the channel length improved cooling performance by enhancing surface interaction. However, the model identified a thermal saturation point at a L/A_p ratio of 1229 m^{-1} , beyond which no significant reduction in outlet temperature was observed, with values stabilizing around $20.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for an inlet temperature of $45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

These findings underscore the critical importance of balancing material selection, geometric optimization, and operating conditions to maximize the performance and sustainability of evaporative cooling systems. Consequently, this work provides valuable guidelines for developing efficient cooling solutions that could substantially contribute

to achieving energy-saving objectives, particularly within net-zero energy building frameworks and related sustainable construction initiatives.

These findings underscore the critical importance of balancing material selection, geometric optimization, and operating conditions to maximize the performance and sustainability of evaporative cooling systems. In particular, the development of thin polymeric wet channels through lamination demonstrates their potential as scalable, durable, and customizable modules for integration into real HVAC systems. Consequently, this work highlights their potential contribution to reducing building cooling loads and supporting the broader objectives of NZEBs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paula Conrat: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Francisco Comino:** Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jesús Castillo-González:** Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Francisco J. Navas-Martos:** Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Manuel Ruiz de Adana:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.139370>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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